

Studies on non-traditional seed oil of *Boswellia serrata*

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Manuscript received 23 April 2008, revised 9 September 2008, accepted 12 November 2008

Abstract : The saponifiable part of the seed oil apart from usual fatty acids, contained two unusual fatty acids – which have been identified as methyl hexadecanoic (1) and octa decadienoic (2) acids, on the basis of mass spectral study of their piconyl ester derivatives. The unsaponifiable part contained stigmastadiene.

Keywords : *Boswellia serrata*, seed oil.

Introduction

In our efforts to screen non-traditional seed oils of the state of Madhya Pradesh, the fatty oil analysis of the seeds of *Boswellia serrata* (Burseraceae) has been undertaken. The gum of this plant is used as diuretic, astringent, in rheumatism and in skin diseases^{1,2}. The alcoholic extract of the root has anticancer activity³.

The seed material was collected from nearby places and authenticated⁴ at the Botany Department, Dr. H. S. Gour University, Sagar.

Results and discussion

Oil was obtained in a yield of 1.2%. The usual saturated acids, identified from the fatty oil are 12 : 0, 14 : 0, 16 : 0, 20 : 0, 22 : 0, 24 : 0 and 26 : 0 – as identified by Co-GC of their Me-esters with standards. The two unusual fatty acids (retention time 7.3 and 10.4 min respectively) did not correspond with the standards and were converted to their picolinyl ester derivatives which were subjected to GC-MS.

Compound 1 with R_t 7.3 min showed molecular ion at m/z 361 and other significant ions at 304 and 332 amu. The difference of 28 amu indicates methyl branch at C-14. These mass ions can be interpreted by considering its structure as 14 methyl-hexadecanoic acid (14 methyl 16 : 0).

Compound 2 with R_t 10.4 min showed molecular ion

at m/z 371 and other significant ions at 178 and 204 and 232 and 258 amu. The difference of 26 amu is due to presence of double bonds at C-5 and C-9 respectively. An ion (m/z 219) is formed by cleavage between two methylene groups that separates the double bonds. These mass ions can be interpreted by considering its structure as 5,9-octadecadienoic acid (5.9–18 : 2).

The HPLC chromatogram of unsaponifiable matter (Fig. 1) shows two peaks – sharp peak (1) is of stigmastadiene, identified after co-chromatography. The wide peak (2) is of wax esters.

Fig. 1

Note

Experimental

The oil from the seeds was extracted with petroleum ether in a Soxhlet extractor. Saponification was carried using KOH/MeOH and the unsaponifiable matter was separated using diethyl ether. The saponifiable part containing mixed fatty acids was subjected to methyl esterification. The methyl ester content was analysed by GC (Varian) using fused silica column, Nitrogen as carrier (1 ml/min) at column temperature of 170 °C. The fatty acids which did not correspond to standards, were separated out on the basis of their retention times and subjected to picolinyl ester derivatization for identification by GC-MS (Shimadzu QP 2000).

The analysis was carried out with a column coating of phenylmethyl silicon, sample injection temperature 80 °C,

programming at 160 °C (30 °C/min) and 325 °C (4 °C/min).

The unsaponifiable matter was subjected to HPLC (Waters) using silicon column. UV detection (217 nm) and hexane : ether (92 : 8) as solvent system (0.2 ml/min flow rate) to identify stigmastadiene by running the standard under identical conditions.

References

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